

Overcoming Regulatory Barriers to the Implementation of AI Agents in Healthcare

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Caption

To facilitate the safe and effective implementation of autonomous AI agents in healthcare, regulatory frameworks must evolve beyond static device paradigms to incorporate adaptive oversight and flexible pathways.

Main

Following the introduction of ChatGPT in 2022, there has been a surge in the research and adoption of large language models (LLMs) and other forms of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI). This trend has also been observed in healthcare, which led to the development of several applications and professional products¹ and their implementation into clinical workflows². Some of these products have a clear medical purpose and, depending on the jurisdiction may qualify as medical devices³, which requires them to meet the high standards set by medical device regulations. These developments have sparked a debate among regulators and researchers about the approvability of such products under current regulatory frameworks¹. Recent approvals, such as the first LLM-enhanced medical device in the EU, demonstrate that applications with a narrow focus and low autonomy can be approved, provided that it is demonstrated that the product's risks are adequately mitigated.

Parallel with these developments, a conceptual shift has emerged that has been recently introduced to healthcare: from viewing GenAI applications as reactive tools to envisioning them as autonomous agents^{4,5}. These *AI agents* or *agent AI systems* can be defined as systems capable of independently

executing and controlling goal-directed workflows on behalf of users with a high degree of autonomy^{6,7}. An AI agent system consists of multiple components, such as external databases and computational tools (e.g., applications for image analysis, note-taking, clinical guidance, and the retrieval and manipulation of patient-sensitive data), which could be orchestrated by one or multiple LLMs, which also handles decision-making, error handling, and recognition of task completion⁴⁻⁷. Since several tasks would fall under the definition of a medical purpose, AI agents in healthcare would often qualify as medical devices and thus be subject to corresponding regulations. However, as the fundamental functioning of AI agents relies on autonomous processes and decisions that are difficult to monitor and model by humans, at least when employed sensibly and to their full potential, the regulation and approval pathway for AI agents is uncertain.

In this paper, we examine whether AI agents can be approved as medical devices under the current regulatory frameworks in the US and Europe and how these frameworks would need to be adapted to facilitate approval.

Regulation under current regulatory frameworks

The regulatory status of AI applications is highly dependent on geography and the use case, meaning that different laws may apply based on the jurisdiction and the application's specific medical purpose. In the healthcare sector, there are two broad types of AI-enabled applications: applications with a non-medical purpose, such as wellness apps and administrative applications (e.g., simple documentation software), and applications with a medical purpose, such as clinical decision support systems (CDSS), therapeutic applications, or diagnosing tools.

Applications with a medical purpose often qualify as medical devices and must comply with medical device-specific laws, such as the EU Medical Device Regulation (MDR) or the Federal Food, Drug & Cosmetic Act (FD&C Act) in the US. Medical devices usually have to follow clearly defined, highly regulated pathways to market, such as 510 (k), De Novo, or full Premarket Approval (PMA) in the US. In addition to medical device-specific laws, AI-enabled medical devices are also subject to general legislation, for example, privacy laws (GDPR (EU), HIPAA (US), etc.) and AI-specific laws (e.g., the EU AI Act).

Since the mid-2010s, an increasing number of AI-enabled medical devices have received approval in the EU and US, most of which have a narrowly defined intended purpose and limited capabilities. Based on the historical decisions, two aspects of the intended purpose could be identified as important for approvability: the scope of the intended purpose (narrow vs. broad) and the degree of autonomy of a system⁸ (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for AI-enabled health applications by degree of autonomy and scope. This figure presents a two-dimensional framework for positioning AI systems in healthcare based on their degree of autonomy (horizontal axis) and scope (vertical axis). The degree of autonomy captures how independently the system operates, ranging from fully human-controlled tools to self-directed systems. In practice, autonomy contains multiple aspects, including operational independence, e.g., of the workflow execution or clinical decision-making authority, which, even in operational autonomous devices, could lay in the responsibility of a human. The scope reflects whether an AI system is narrowly optimised for a single task or capable of performing multiple, generalised functions across domains. Traditional applications tend to cluster in the narrow/low-autonomy quadrant and are typically aligned with current regulatory pathways. In contrast, GenAI-based systems and AI agents often reside in the broad/high-autonomy quadrant, where they introduce regulatory challenges. The provided examples are based on devices described in the literature and on-market devices. The list is not exhaustive. ¹Would fall under non-device status in the US.

Narrow and non-autonomous AI-enabled health applications are approvable under current regulations and pathways⁸, albeit with some difficulties. This also applies to some GenAI applications, as demonstrated by the first approval of narrow and non-autonomous GenAI applications in the EU and the UK. Even individual narrow, near-autonomous and autonomous systems that are not GenAI have been approved but often fall into high-risk classes⁸.

In contrast, the approval of broad AI systems is more problematic, as current regulatory frameworks are designed for products that have a narrow scope, are not adaptive, keep human oversight, and do not evolve after their placement on the market^{5,9}. This would apply to meaningful GenAI applications, as they tend to have a broader scope due to the general-purpose capabilities of the underlying model. AI agents built with GenAI models are not only broad in scope but, by definition, also possess a high degree of autonomy in their operative processes and have the ability to respond and produce a wide range of inputs and outputs for which they have not been specifically designed (**Figure 1**). These characteristics lead to a range of benefits and risks that are different in their nature than for previously considered applications (**Table 1**)⁴.

Table 1. Characteristics of AI agents in healthcare. This table outlines key characteristics of AI agents in healthcare, some of which are specific to AI agents, while others are also relevant to GenAI applications in general. All characteristics carry risks, while some also carry benefits. Targeted risk-reduction strategies are described

Characteristic	Affects agents in particular	Benefits	Risks	Risk-reduction strategies
Bias ^{4,9}	No	-	Biases in training data may lead to wrong or dangerous recommendations or actions.	Conduct bias audits, use representative training data, and include fairness metrics in validation ³ .
Overreliance ^{4,9}	No	-	Users may place excessive trust in AI outputs, even when inappropriate or incorrect.	Design interfaces that highlight uncertainty, maintain clinician oversight and support interpretability.es
Hallucination ⁹	No	-	AI agents may generate plausible but incorrect or misleading outputs.	Incorporate guardrails, retrieval-augmented generation, and post-processing validation steps ³ .
Non-determinism	No	Enables generative	Agents may produce different	Reduce model stochasticity (e.g.,

and lack of predictability ³		flexibility, contextual adaptation, and nuanced outputs across a wide range of tasks	outputs when given the same input across runs due to the minimally restricted range of potential inputs and outputs.	temperature); use modular, role-based agent systems to structure reasoning ⁶ .
Reduced human oversight ⁴	Yes	Enables automation and scalability.	Limits human control and ability to intervene; may reduce accountability.	Use human-in-the-loop (HITL) or human-on-the-loop (HOTL) oversight tailored to task risks ⁴ ; define agent responsibilities and boundaries and ensure ethical oversight ^{4,8} ; ensure ethical oversight.
Higher adaptability ⁴	Yes	Facilitates personalization, learning from deployment contexts, and performance.	Complicates validation and reduces predictability.	Limit adaptability and purpose; apply pre-determined change control plans where applicable; create benchmarks appropriate real-world conditions.
Error propagation ⁴	Yes	-	Errors in one subsystem can propagate through the entire system.	Use stress-testing and hierarchical validation and simulate worst-case scenarios to assess propagating failures ⁴ .
Modularity	Yes	Enhances scalability, reuse, adaptability, and performance through specialization of components	Multiple interacting subsystems increase certification complexity and risk of unintended behaviours.	Apply component- and system-level certification; clearly define subsystem roles and safety checks.
Cybersecurity and Privacy	No	-	AI agents can leak or misuse sensitive data if not properly designed; this risk grows with personalisation.	Use local and distilled models when feasible, e.g., on-premise or edge deployment ¹ ; adopt privacy-by-design principles and security audits.

Overall, it can be expected that AI agents with an intended use that qualifies them as medical devices face significant regulatory approval hurdles. Systems with a narrowly defined scope and low degree of autonomy have a more straightforward path to approval, as they resemble on-market, non-agentic AI tools. However, the deployment of ‘true’ AI agents, which are both autonomous and broad in scope, will likely remain impossible without substantial changes to current regulatory frameworks.

A Way Forward: Regulating AI Agents in Healthcare

To allow the implementation of AI agents in healthcare, policymakers and regulatory authorities will need to explore modifications of existing regulatory frameworks or the development of new ones. These changes must align with the two primary goals of regulatory regimes for medical devices: minimising the risk of patient harm and providing clear requirements for developers that enable safe innovation. Some approaches have already been proposed to appropriately oversee GenAI-enabled medical devices and are currently being tested by regulatory authorities^{1,4,10}. While these proposed strategies can be partially adapted, additional considerations are necessary to address the complexity and novelty of AI agent architectures (**Figure 2a**).

Figure 2. Potential adaptations to current regulatory frameworks. a) The strategies described are distributed along the axes of impact and feasibility. Voluntary alternative pathways (VAPs) could be considered the most promising strategy (green), while other strategies lack feasibility or impact. b) The concept of VAPs is depicted in more detail. Developers could either choose the alternative pathway if their device qualifies for it or stick to an established pathway to seek certification, clearance, or approval as a medical device¹. Based on device risk, performance, or the manufacturer's behaviour, regulators can move the device from the VAP to the appropriate standard pathway.

Minor to medium changes to regulatory frameworks suitable for AI agents could include the rational extension of the existing concept of ‘enforcement discretion’ and the rational, risk-based qualification of certain devices as non-medical devices. Enforcement discretion refers to a practice already used by the FDA, in which authorities acknowledge that a product qualifies as a medical device but choose not to enforce certain regulatory requirements. In contrast, non-device classification means that a device falls outside of the scope of medical device regulations, even when it has a medical purpose. This model has already been adopted in the US to exempt specific healthcare professional-facing CDSS from being classified as medical devices if they inform but do not override clinician judgment¹¹. The FDA has issued final guidance, which makes a conservative interpretation of this law, limiting its applicability to GenAI systems¹¹ and advanced autonomous AI agents. A blanket enforcement discretion or non-device approach for sophisticated AI agents is unlikely to be appropriate, given their potential impact on clinical decision-making and workflow. Instead, a clearer definition and less conservative interpretation of the boundary between non-medical devices and medical devices could assist developers and regulators in classifying edge cases more consistently.

More tailored approaches may emerge through alternative regulatory pathways, including frameworks explicitly designed for AI-enabled medical devices. The FDA has already called for the development of corresponding laws, and researchers have proposed several mechanisms, such as voluntary alternative pathways (VAPs)¹ and adaptive pathways¹². These are not intended to replace existing approval pathways but to supplement them, thereby avoiding the need for significant alterations to the entire regulatory framework (**Figure 2b**). Manufacturers can then decide which pathway they want to follow. The advantage is that VAPs can be designed to better test the specific aspects of a product, e.g. GenAI or AI agents, through new approaches. Based on device risk, performance, or the manufacturer's behaviour, regulators can move the device from the VAP to a standard pathway. Cho et al. have proposed such an approach for integrated devices, which differs from previous pathways in that it involves a two-stage review process¹. Adaptive pathways shift the regulatory paradigm from static pre-market approval to dynamic oversight through real-world performance data, stakeholder collaboration, and iterative updates. This concept can be extended to agentic AI systems as their risk profile could only be fully understood post-deployment.

Predetermined Change Control Plans (PCCPs) are a concept that has already been implemented in the US¹³. They allow for changes to an approved, on-market medical device that were predicted and predefined in a plan submitted with the medical device application without requiring a new approval process¹³. This concept is only partially applicable to the adaptive nature of AI agents and has substantial limitations, as changes are often not predictable at the time of submission. The same

applies to the concept of regulatory sandboxes, which are tools for testing new technologies and ways to regulate them in environments with fewer regulatory requirements¹⁰. They are already employed by multiple national regulatory authorities in pilot projects such as the UK AI Airlock program and are recognised as a relevant instrument in the EU AI Act. However, while this instrument facilitates the evaluation of highly novel devices and, in some cases, allows the refinement of regulations, it is not an ideal or scalable permanent solution for the widespread use of AI agents due to the resources and commitment required by regulators.

A broader approach, recently proposed by Ayers, Desai, and Smith (2024), was to shift regulatory focus from technical compliance to demonstrable patient-centred outcomes¹⁴. However, this strategy has the downside of limiting regulatory decisions to a subset of metrics that are already part of a complex decision paradigm. A purely outcome-driven approach neglects the potential of harm to patients, especially for hard-to-quantifiable risks, and no differentiation is made between devices with different risk profiles.

A more progressive, if not radical, idea is to regulate GenAI applications analogously to human clinicians¹⁵. Other researchers have recently suggested utilising this concept for future regulatory frameworks for AI agents, where such systems would undergo a structured “training” process similar to medical education: exposure to validated learning content, tailored assessments, supervised real-life practice, and periodic re-evaluation, implemented as a series of progressive approvals, allowing systems to gain more autonomy only after demonstrating safe and effective performance^{4,5}. While compelling, such a paradigm raises critical questions about accountability, a central aspect in the training of humans. Both trainers and trainees can face professional, legal, and reputational consequences if the expected level of quality is not met or misconduct occurs. To avoid bad actors just relaunching under a new identity or rebranding their flawed device, mechanisms for accountability are required. These could include obligatory public registries, certification schemes similar to the ones already in place for medical devices, or financial surety bonds similar to the ones used in the Medicare program for suppliers of Durable Medical Equipment, Prosthetics, Orthotics, and Supplies. For AI agents, a regulatory authority could draw on the bond in case of misbehaviour to compensate patients or systems for harm and penalise the manufacturer. However, these paradigms remain aspirational in the short term and would require major policy, institutional, and infrastructural changes.

Conclusion

While GenAI models have initiated substantial developments in healthcare, their current use remains limited. AI agents, with their autonomy, adaptability, and broader scope, are expected to drive the

next transformation. However, within existing regulatory frameworks, their deployment remains largely unfeasible. Incremental regulatory steps may permit the approval of restricted applications, but realising the full potential of AI agents in healthcare will require bold and forward-thinking reforms. Regulators must start preparing now to both safeguard patient safety and promote responsible innovation.

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OF, SJ, JNK, and SG developed the concept of the manuscript. OF and SJ conducted the literature search. OF and SJ drew the figures. OF and SJ wrote the first draft of the manuscript. All authors contributed to the writing, interpretation of the content, and editing of the manuscript, revising it critically for important intellectual content. All authors had final approval of the completed version. The authors take accountability for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

Competing interests

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